

ECONOMIC EVALUATION OF PIGEONPEA (*Cajanus cajan* (L.) Millsp) BASED NUTRI-CEREALS INTERCROPPING IN MEDIUM BLACK SOIL

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Abstract

A field experiment was carried out to study the economic evaluation of pigeonpea [*Cajanus cajan* (L.) Millsp] based nutri-cereals intercropping in medium black soil at research farm of Dr. Sharadchandra Pawar College of Agriculture, Baramati during kharif season 2023-24. The result revealed that higher pigeonpea equivalent yield (PEY) and land equivalent ratio (LER) was recorded in pigeonpea + foxtail millet intercropping system with a 1:4 row ratio. The intercropping system of pigeonpea + foxtail millet (1:4) yielded significantly higher gross monetary returns (194508 ₹ ha⁻¹), net monetary returns (134479 ₹ ha⁻¹) and B:C ratio (3.24) compared to other treatments.

Key words: B:C; millets; pigeonpea; intercropping; pigeonpea equivalent yield; yield

Introduction

Pigeonpea is a kharif pulse crop grown in semi-arid tropical region. It is better called as red gram, Tur, Arhar, no eye pea (*Cajanus cajan* var. *flvus*). India contributes for about 72% of area grown to pigeonpea (Fatokimi *et al.*, 2021).

Pigeonpea is a significant nitrogen-fixing legume because it enhances soil nutrient status and draws moisture and minerals from the soil's deeper layers through its deep root system. Traditionally it is called as "Biological plough" and "Kalpavriksha" of rainfed areas because all the parts are beneficial in one or the other way, other benefits like food and dried branches can be used as fuel and thatching material and also for making baskets. Pigeonpea is traditionally grown in wide spacing under rainfed conditions. (Vinay *et al.*, 2021).

In today's agricultural scenario growing grains or cereals as the sole crop is not profitable. To address the wide range of consumer demand and the ever-increasing population, pulses must be included in cereal production systems. Although the cereal + legumes intercropping method is widely advertised as crop failure insurance for monocultures in rainfed regions, the primary objective of intercropping is to assure better and more sustainable output. (Kushwaha and Mehta, 2023).

Millets are traditional field crops in India. These are well known as "Nutri-cereals" as they are an abundant source of micronutrients, minerals and vitamin B-Complex. Their natural ability to mature earlier, yield more due to C4 mechanism, produce better even in low fertile soil under poor management and withstand low, irregular rainfall have all drawn significant attention to them in recent years. (Vinay *et al.*, 2021).

Intercropping involves cultivating two or more crops together on the same piece of land with specific row arrangements. It aims to improve productivity and profitability by efficiently using resources and maintaining soil health. The inclusion of pulses in intercropping with millets has a positive effect regarding productivity, economics and fertility status of the soil. It can be referred to as biological insurance against various risks that prevail in rainfed agriculture. (Bhargav *et al.*, 2018)

Intercropping stands out as an effective method to boost yields without significantly raising input usage. It involves cultivating multiple crops together on the same plot, leading to intensified crop growth through both timing and spatial arrangement. Alongside benefits such as diversification, labour management, soil fertility preservation. Intercropping offers higher productivity and enhanced stability by maximizing the utilization of solar energy, moisture, and nutrients. (Bhagat *et al.*, 2019).

Material methods

A field experiment was carried out at research farm of Dr. Sharadchandra Pawar College of Agriculture, Baramati during kharif season 2023-24 to assess the economic evaluation of pigeonpea [*Cajanus cajan* (L.) Millsp] based nutri-cereals intercropping in medium black soil. The soil texture of the experimental field was clayey with medium organic carbon content (0.54%) and a somewhat alkaline pH (8.2) along with electrical conductivity of 0.32 ds m⁻¹. It

had low available nitrogen (220.8 kg ha⁻¹), moderate available phosphorus (19.8 kg ha⁻¹), and high available potassium (420.23 kg ha⁻¹). The total rainfall during the cropping season amounted to 450.30 mm.

The experimental plot had a flat topography, black, deep, well drained soil making it suitable for pigeonpea cultivation. The experiment was conducted using a randomized block design (RBD) with nine treatments *viz.*, T₁-Sole pigeonpea (BDN 2013-41), T₂-Sole finger millet (KMR 301), T₃-Sole foxtail millet (DHFT 20-3), T₄-Sole barnyard millet (DHBM 47-3), T₅-Sole pearl millet (Dhansakti), T₆-Pigeonpea+finger millet (1:4), T₇-Pigeonpea + foxtail millet (1:4), T₈-Pigeonpea + barnyard millet (1:4), T₉-Pigeonpea + pearl millet (1:3). Each treatment was replicated four times. The experimental field had a gross and net size of 9.3 m x 9 m and 8.1 m x 5.4 m respectively. Pigeonpea and nutri-cereals was sown on broad bed furrow using the dibbling method on July 21, 2023. The spacing for sowing was 180 cm x 30 cm for pigeonpea, 30 cm x 10 cm for all nutri-cereals except pearl millet which was spaced at 45 cm x 15 cm.

The observation on growth and yield were taken from the net plots and the grain yield of the different crops was converted to hectare basis in quintals. The economics of each system were calculated using the current market prices of that year.

The yield was further calculated in terms of pigeonpea equivalent yield (PEY), land equivalent ratio (LER), gross and net monetary returns and the B:C ratio to evaluate system productivity.

The calculation is performed using the following formula

$$PEY = \frac{\text{Yield of millets (q ha}^{-1}) \times \text{Price of millets (q}^{-1})}{\text{Price of pigeonpea (q}^{-1})} + \text{Yield of pigeonpea (q ha}^{-1})$$

$$LER = \frac{\text{Yield of pigeonpea in Intercropping system}}{\text{Yield of sole pigeonpea}} + \frac{\text{Yield of millets in intercropping system}}{\text{Yield of sole millets}}$$

Result and discussion

Pigeonpea and nutri-cereal seed yield

The results revealed that significantly higher seed yield of pigeonpea (20.45 q ha⁻¹) was recorded with treatment T₁ (Sole pigeonpea). Among intercropping systems, treatment T₉ (Pigeonpea + pearl millet) with 1:3 row ratio recorded higher seed yield (16.09 q ha⁻¹) which was at par with treatment T₇ (Pigeonpea + foxtail millet) with 1:4 row ratio *i.e.* 15.64 q ha⁻¹ (Table 1). Further, treatment T₃ (Sole foxtail millet) recorded significantly higher seed yield *i.e.* 23.92 q ha⁻¹. However, lower seed yield was recorded in treatment T₈ (Pigeonpea + barnyard millet) with 1:4 row ratio *i.e.* 13.85 q ha⁻¹ compared to other treatments except treatment T₉ (Pigeonpea + pearl millet) with 1:3 row ratio *i.e.* 14.21 q ha⁻¹.

Pigeonpea equivalent yield

Intercropping systems generally offer higher crop equivalent yield compared to sole cropping system as long as the row ratio is optimized

and companion crops are chosen scientifically. The data on the pigeonpea equivalent yield under sole and intercropping systems are detailed in Table 1.

There was significant difference in pigeonpea equivalent yield among the sole and intercropping systems. However, significantly higher pigeonpea equivalent yield (26.00 q ha⁻¹) was recorded in treatment T₇ (Pigeonpea + foxtail millet) with 1:4 row ratio compared to other treatments (Table 1). Among intercropping systems, lower pigeonpea equivalent yield (20.27 q ha⁻¹) were observed in treatment T₈ (Pigeonpea + barnyard millet) with 1:4 row ratio.

Among various sole nutri-cereals, the treatment T₂ (Sole finger millet) was recorded highest pigeonpea equivalent yield (12.79 kg ha⁻¹) which was at par with treatment T₃ (Sole foxtail millet) i.e. 11.96 q ha⁻¹ and significantly outperformed sole barnyard millet (8.47 q ha⁻¹) and sole pearl millet (6.35 q ha⁻¹).

Pigeonpea + foxtail millet (1:4 row ratio) intercropping system recorded highest pigeonpea equivalent yield because of increased grain yields of component crops attributed to optimal nutrient availability and higher market price of both the crops, contributed to enhanced pigeonpea equivalent yield. The results are congruence with the findings of Biradar *et al.* (2020) who reported that maximum pigeonpea equivalent yield (PEY) was recorded by pigeonpea + foxtail millet intercropping system with 1:2 row ratio.

Land equivalent ratio

The land equivalent ratio (LER) is the ratio of the area required for sole cropping to produce same yield as intercropping under similar management conditions. LER is a key index for evaluating yield benefits, offering a consistent measure of the overall biological efficiency of an intercropping system.

Intercropping system of pigeonpea + foxtail millet (T₇) in 1:4 row ratio was recorded highest land equivalent ratio (1.64) which was at par with treatment T₉ (Pigeonpea+ pearl millet) in 1:3 row ratio i.e. 1.59 than other treatments (Table 1). Among different cropping systems, pigeonpea + foxtail millet (1:4 row ratio) intercropping system reported higher land equivalent ratio. This could be attributed to the higher yields of pigeonpea and foxtail millet in intercropping systems, as well as the greater land utilization accomplished through intercropping compared to sole cropping. Equivalent findings were also noted by Sowmiya *et al.* (2024) and Biradar *et al.* (2020) concluded that pigeonpea + foxtail millet intercropping system with 1:2 row ratio recorded significantly higher LER for both years i.e. 2017 and 2018.

Economics

Economic analysis calculated using current market prices of inputs and outputs revealed significant differences in profitability across various cropping systems (Table 2)

Among different cropping systems, treatment T₇ (Pigeonpea + foxtail millet) with 1:4 row ratio recorded significantly higher gross monetary returns (194508 ₹ ha⁻¹), net monetary return (134479 ₹ ha⁻¹) and B:C ratio (3.24) compared to other treatments, while lowest gross monetary returns (57480 ₹ ha⁻¹), net monetary returns (13603 ₹ ha⁻¹) and B:C ratio (1.31) were obtained from treatment T₅ (Sole pearl millet). This

could be attributed to the higher market price of both pigeonpea as well as foxtail millet and the reduced cost of cultivation in these treatments. Similar insights were also reported by Manjunath and Kalaghatigi (2018), Biradar *et al.* (2020), Vinay *et al.* (2021).

Conclusion

The intercropping system resulted in a considerably higher pigeonpea equivalent yield, land equivalent ratio and benefit cost ratio compared to sole cropping. The data concluded that pigeonpea + foxtail millet (1:4) intercropping system proved to be the most effective resulting in higher net monetary returns (134479 ₹ ha⁻¹) and B:C ratio (3.24) compared to other intercropping treatments. Hence it was concluded that intercropping of pigeonpea with foxtail millet in 1:4 row ratio rather than growing pigeonpea alone could be a more viable and economically profitable cropping system.

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Table 1: Seed yield, pigeonpea equivalent yield and land equivalent ratio as influenced by pigeonpea based nutri-cereal intercropping systems.

Treatment	Seed yield (q ha ⁻¹)		Pigeonpea equivalent yield (q ha ⁻¹)	Land equivalent ratio
	Pigeonpea	Nutri-cereal		
T ₁ -Sole pigeonpea	20.45	-	20.45	1.00
T ₂ -Sole finger millet	-	21.32	12.79	1.00
T ₃ -Sole foxtail millet	-	23.92	11.96	1.00
T ₄ -Sole barnyard millet	-	16.94	8.47	1.00
T ₅ -Sole pearl millet	-	17.78	6.35	1.00
T ₆ -Pigeonpea + finger millet (1:4)	12.48	19.07	23.92	1.51
T ₇ -Pigeonpea + foxtail millet (1:4)	15.64	20.74	26.00	1.64
T ₈ -Pigeonpea + barnyard millet (1:4)	13.34	13.85	20.27	1.48
T ₉ -Pigeonpea + pearl millet (1:3)	16.09	14.21	21.17	1.59
S.E.m ±	0.55	0.68	0.52	0.04
C.D. at 5 %	1.69	2.00	1.52	0.11
General mean	15.60	18.48	16.82	1.25

Table 2: Economics of pigeonpea based nutri-cereal intercropping systems.

Treatment	Gross monetary returns (₹ ha ⁻¹)	Cost of cultivation (₹ ha ⁻¹)	Net monetary returns (₹ ha ⁻¹)	B:C ratio
T ₁ -Sole pigeonpea	147902	53140	94762	2.78
T ₂ -Sole finger millet	99513	46931	52582	2.12
T ₃ -Sole foxtail millet	93782	45895	47887	2.04
T ₄ -Sole barnyard millet	68839	43775	25064	1.57
T ₅ -Sole pearl millet	57480	43877	13603	1.31
T ₆ -Pigeonpea + finger millet (1:4)	179250	60111	119139	2.98
T ₇ -Pigeonpea + foxtail millet (1:4)	194508	60029	134479	3.24
T ₈ -Pigeonpea + barnyard millet (1:4)	153337	56001	97336	2.74
T ₉ -Pigeonpea + pearl millet (1:3)	163856	58725	105131	2.79
S.E.m ±	3786	-	3786	-
C.D. at 5 %	11051	-	11051	-
General mean	128718	-	76665	-